

LEARNING ACTION CELL IMPLEMENTATION AND TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE IN QUEZON IV DISTRICT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 4

Pages: 487-495

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3075

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14898103

Manuscript Accepted: 01-30-2025

Learning Action Cell Implementation and Teachers' Performance in Quezon IV District

Marchelle E. Baguio,* Aida C. Selecios

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study examined the performance of teachers in the conduct of LAC in Performance in the LAC Implementation in their respective school and/or grade level. Likewise, it measures its relationship to the performance of teachers in the IPCRF comprising the four Key Result Areas (KRAs) during the school year 2021-2022 in the Quezon IV district, Division of Bukidnon. A total of 147 teachers from 9 barangays and 9 elementary schools were taken as participants of the study. The descriptive-quantitative method of research was utilized in treating the data to answer the specific problems posted in chapter one. Data gathered on the scores of performances in LAC implementation that relative to Content and Pedagogy, Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion, Relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization, Performance in the LAC Implementation Relative to Assessment and Reporting. Furthermore, it evaluated significant relationship between the teachers' extent of performance in LAC implementation and the teacher's Individual Performance and Review. The study found out that the LAC performance relative to Relative to Content and Pedagogy is 4.32 qualitatively describes High Extent of Implementation, Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion has 4.31, LAC implementation Performance Relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization has mean 4.26, LAC implementation Performance in the LAC Implementation Relative to Assessment and Reporting is 4.32 qualitatively describe very high extent of implementation. Relatively the LAC implementation is generally described high extent of implementation. The study also revealed that four key result areas on the performance of teachers has an equivalent adjectival rating of very satisfactory. The study finally found out that there was a strong significant relationship between the extent of LAC implementation, and the four key result area of the teachers' performance.

Keywords: *LAC, implementation, teacher, performance*

Introduction

The challenging role of teachers and educators in quest of quality education for lifelong learning of students in the fast evolution of the global competence, has led to the creation of several programs in the Department of Education to answer and assist the teachers' proficiency in classroom instructions. One of the most fascinating directives from DepEd is the learning action cell.

The Learning Action Cell (LAC) is consistently carried out by executing it on an in-person learning modality at least once every month. According to Department of Education Order No. 35, s. 2016, a learning action cell is a meeting led by a group of teachers who work together to address common problems they encounter at school. These difficulties could relate to learner diversity and student inclusion, curriculum and pedagogy, evaluation and reporting, and the incorporation of Information and Communication Technologies and 21st-century skills. These Learning Action Cell sessions are intended to be a school-based continuing professional development technique for enhancing teaching and learning, according to Department of Education.

Department of Education suggests that each teacher should receive sufficient guidance and training in the teaching and learning processes by revisiting or revising certain topics or by being concerned with carrying out the obligations and responsibilities of an effective and efficient teacher. The systematic application of effective methods for communicating and evaluating the lesson's intended learning outcomes results in effective teaching, according to Silva (2018).

This Learning Action Cell (LAC) is very important on improving the teaching and learning process, it prepares the teachers for globalization. Their attendance to these seminars will help create an effective environment, improve teaching-learning situations, keep updated on modern instructional devices and inspire them to become better teachers in the modern world, (Madriaga, K 2021).

It is hope that this study will gather facts and assess the impact of conducting Learning Action Cell sessions and how it influences the professional growth of teachers and most of all to the individual performance of teachers at the end of the school year. It also expected that this study will serve as an ally for teachers' instructional competence and take advantage of their strength to meet the smartness of the students in the present generation. The future awaits a variety of opportunities for the students in different expertise and talents in them, thus diversity of students should be responded and accommodated by the teachers.

Research Questions

In accordance with DepEd order No. 035 s. 2016, the purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of Learning Action Cells and to ascertain how they affect teachers' performance in their Results-Based Performance Management Systems (RPMS) through Individual Performance Commitment and Review Forms (IPCRF). More specifically, it will attempt to address the following questions:

1. What is the extent of Learning Action Cell implementation in the context of Content and Pedagogy; Learner Diversity and

Student Inclusion; Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization; and Learning Action Cell Implementation Relative to Assessment and Reporting?

2. What is the teacher's Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form rating for school year 2021-2022?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of Learning Action Cell implementation and the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form rating?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive- quantitative method of research through the use survey research design. Fraenkel and Wallen (2006) emphasizes that survey research design is used in studying a large group of individuals particularly how it is distributed to one or more variables or characteristics. This design will be used in the study through the utilization of questionnaire checklists. It will be distributed and accomplished by the teachers in Quezon IV District, on the LAC activities of teachers, and their performance rating in the 4 key result areas.

Respondents

Purposive sampling was used in the study. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by school.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents in School

No.	Name of School	No. of Teachers
1	Apyao Elementary School	31
2	Busco Central Elementary School	36
3	Butong Elementary School	17
4	Dumalama Elementary School	6
5	Kipaypayon Elementary School	6
6	Lumintao Elementary School	14
7	Paitan Integrated School	18
8	Salaysay Integrated School	12
9	Sto. Domingo Elementary School	7
Total		147

Instrument

There are two sections to the research tool. Part I covered A. 10 items on the LAC Implementation Performance with Regard to Content and Pedagogy; B. 13 performance metrics for the LAC implementation that pertain to learner diversity and student inclusion; C. 10 questions about how well the LAC implementation of the curriculum was contextualized, indigenous, and localized; and D. 8 performance-related items related to assessment and reporting for the LAC implementation.

Part II contains teacher performance evaluations within the framework of KRA 1. Pedagogy and Content Knowledge, KRA 2. Environment for Learning, KRA 3. Learning diversity, curriculum planning, assessment, and reporting, as well as KRA 4. in connections with the community, professional engagement, personal development, and professional growth. The instrument used was an adopted instrument by Binauhan, R. C. (2019) from her study "Learning Action Cell Implementation In The Public Elementary Schools In The Division Of Cavite

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer on the conduct of teachers LAC. On the Performance of teachers in 4 Key Result Areas, mean and percentage were used. On the significant relationship between the conduct of LAC and performance rating of teachers, Pearson-Correlation was used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered from the teachers of Quezon IV District, Quezon, Bukidnon. The presentation provides information on the teachers' response on the implementation of Learning Action Cell (LAC) and Teacher's Performance in Quezon IV District.

The extent of LAC implementation in the context of; Relative to Content and Pedagogy, Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion, Relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization, Performance in the LAC Implementation Relative to Assessment and Reporting.

Table 2 presents the data of LAC implementation pertaining to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. Table 2 revealed the three highest mean 4.50 on the indicator Master content and performance standards and learning competencies, the mean of 4.46 on Plan lessons and delivering instructions effectively and the mean 4.45 on the indicator Implement developmentally appropriate teaching methods that respect individual differences of the learners. It is Qualitatively described Very High Extent of Implementation. This implies that

these indicators have implemented in most instances of the teacher’s LAC sessions. The standard deviation observed in all indicators is less than 0.68 baseline standard deviation which means that the teachers’ responses were very close the mean.

Table 2. *The Extent of LAC Implementation Relative to Content and Pedagogy*

Indicator	Mean	SD (Standard Deviation)	Qualitative Description
1. Study and analyze the Kto12 Curriculum	4.25	0.617	Very High Extent of Implementation
2. Prepare for lessons and be more relaxed in executing lesson plans	4.24	0.676	Very High Extent of Implementation
3. Implement developmentally appropriate teaching methods that respect individual differences of the learners	4.45	0.610	Very High Extent of Implementation
4. Jointly craft learning goals in collaboration with their learners	4.31	0.658	Very High Extent of Implementation
5. Master content and performance standards and learning competencies	4.50	2.460	Very High Extent of Implementation
6. Plan lessons and delivering instructions effectively	4.46	0.589	Very High Extent of Implementation
7. Assess the learning that resulted from their teaching	4.38	0.657	Very High Extent of Implementation
8. Plan weekly lessons during the LAC which can be implemented for a specified period	4.12	0.667	High Extent of Implementation
9. Share their experiences to improve subsequent lessons	4.33	0.686	Very High Extent of Implementation
10. Translate curriculum content into relevant learning activities	4.19	0.665	High Extent of Implementation
Overall	4.32		Very High Extent of Implementation

Legend: 4.20–5.00 – Very High Extent of Implementation | 3.40–4.19 – High Extent of Implementation | 2.60–3.39 – Moderate Extent of Implementation | 1.80–2.59 – Low Extent of Implementation | 1.00–1.79 – No Implementation
 Note: N=147

Table 3 presents the performance of teachers in LAC implementation relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion. It is demonstrated in table 3 that the three highest mean are as follows; 4.47 on the indicator, Emphasize that learners are the reason for all education process, the mean of 4.46 on indicator Differentiate their instruction to include all learners and the mean 4.38 on the indicator Address the learners needs as to strength, interests and experiences. It is Qualitatively described Very High Extent of Implementation. This implies that the teachers tackled these indicators in their LAC sessions. The standard deviations of the indicators observed in all indicators is less than 0.68 baseline standard which means that the teacher’s responses are very close to the mean.

Table 3. *The Extent of LAC Implementation Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion*

Indicators	Mean	SD (Standard Deviation)	Qualitative Description
1. Include learner diversity and student inclusion as topic for discussion in the session	4.34	0.579	Very High Extent of Implementation
2. Emphasize that learners are the reason for all education process	4.47	0.600	Very High Extent of Implementation
3. Establish learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity	4.37	0.695	Very High Extent of Implementation
4. Underscore the importance of teacher’s knowledge and understanding of learners’ characteristics and experiences	4.18	0.699	High Extent of Implementation
5. Discuss that diversity emanates from a variety of factors such as gender, community membership, religious beliefs, family configurations and special learning needs	4.26	0.693	Very High Extent of Implementation
6. Celebrate diversity in their classrooms	4.16	0.811	High Extent of Implementation
7. Differentiate their instruction to include all learners	4.46	0.622	Very High Extent of Implementation
8. Adjust their instruction to foster harmony in class	4.36	0.641	High Extent of Implementation
9. Provide remedial instruction for those who are experiencing difficulties in learning lessons	4.34	0.736	Very High Extent of Implementation
10. Prevent failure and communicating with their learners	4.18	0.738	High Extent of Implementation
11. Address the learners need as to strength, interests and experiences	4.38	0.703	Very High Extent of Implementation
12. Give additional information on the different indigenous groups	4.23	0.703	Very High Extent of Implementation
13. Encourage learners to be holistically developed learners	4.33	0.704	Very High Extent of Implementation
Overall	4.31		Very High Extent of Implementation

Legend: 4.20–5.00 – Very High Extent of Implementation | 3.40–4.19 – High Extent of Implementation | 2.60–3.39 – Moderate Extent of Implementation | 1.80–2.59 – Low Extent of Implementation | 1.00–1.79 – No Implementation
 Note: N=147

The over-all performance in implementing LAC relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion has mean 4.31 and is qualitatively describe Very High Extent of Implementation. The composite performance in implementing LAC relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion has mean 4.31 and is qualitatively describe very high extent of implementation. The findings of Silva, V.C (2021) about as a key for teacher’s professional development was conducted to determine the needs of teachers in terms of learner’s diversity

and inclusion, content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting is needed in SLAC and maybe given a priority.

Table 4 presents the performance of teachers in the implementation of LAC relative to Curriculum Contextualization Indigenization and Localization.

Table 4. LAC Implementation Performance Relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization

Indicators	Mean	SD (Standard Deviation)	Qualitative Description
1. Match the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to teachers	4.31	0.648	Very High Extent of Implementation
2. Identify and responds to opportunities to link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests, and aspiration of the wider school community and other key stakeholders	4.27	0.647	Very High Extent of Implementation
3. Link new content to the local experiences that are familiar to learners to make learning more efficient and relevant	4.24	0.634	Very High Extent of Implementation
4. Modify teacher's guide and learners' materials to accommodate the unique contexts of a particular locality	4.29	0.654	Very High Extent of Implementation
5. Prepare curricula materials suited to the cultural and social context in which they teach, actively	4.24	0.678	Very High Extent of Implementation
6. Recognize that the K to 12 Curriculum is learner- centered, inclusive, and research-based	4.31	0.628	Very High Extent of Implementation
7. Realize that the K to 12 Curriculum is flexible, ICT based and global	4.32	0.653	Very High Extent of Implementation
8. Make sure that the members of the community participate in indigenization processes, so that the curriculum will be accurate and faithful to the culture in consideration	4.19	0.686	High Extent of Implementation
9. Inculcate that the K to 12 Curriculum is culture responsive and culture sensitive, integrative and contextualized, relevant and responsive; and	4.25	0.639	Very High Extent of Implementation
10. Work towards an implementation of a curriculum that is competence-based, seamless and decongested	4.22	0.700	Very High Extent of Implementation
Overall	4.26		Very High Extent of Implementation

Legend: 4.20–5.00 – Very High Extent of Implementation | 3.40–4.19 – High Extent of Implementation | 2.60–3.39 – Moderate Extent of Implementation | 1.80–2.59 – Low Extent of Implementation | 1.00–1.79 – No Implementation
 Note: N=147

Table 4 reveals that the indicator Realize that the K to 12 Curriculum is flexible, ICT based and global has the highest mean 4.32 and is qualitatively described Very High Extent of Implementation. This implies that implementers of LAC give emphasis of ICT as a strong bond for a globally competent individual. This finding is backed by a number of studies, and schools and other educational institutions that aim to educate students for life in "a knowledge society" should think about integrating ICT into their curricula, according to S. Ghavifekr. et al (2012). The mean for the LAC implementers performance relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization has average mean 4.26 and qualitatively describe Very High Extent of Implementation. Numerous research have also confirmed this conclusion. From UNESCO, Pariscal, D. R., et al. (2022) highlighted that educators are increasingly in agreement about the value of contextualizing instruction. UNESCO has frequently pushed for educational reforms that respect and take into account local contexts, traditions, and values as well as their relevance to students.

Table 5 presents the LAC implementers performance pertaining to Assessment and Reporting.

Table 5. The Extent of LAC Implementation Performance in the LAC Implementation Relative to Assessment and Reporting

	Mean	SD (Standard Deviation)	Qualitative Description
1. Implement the learner-centered assessment policies for the Kto12 Curriculum	4.381	0.612	Very High Extent of Implementation
2. Include ways in assessing the learners during LAC sessions data from formative assessment to devise interventions	4.259	0.653	Very High Extent of Implementation
3. Conduct assessment that provides teachers and learners with the necessary feedback about learning outcomes	4.279	0.649	Very High Extent of Implementation
4. Selects, organizes and uses sound assessment continuously.	4.306	0.637	Very High Extent of Implementation
5. Measure their effectiveness based on learners' result	4.347	0.659	Very High Extent of Implementation
6. Use learners output as evidence to improve professional practice	4.327	0.643	Very High Extent of Implementation
7. Set target on desired learners progress	4.367	0.663	Very High Extent of Implementation
8. Identify the evidence needed to show learners understanding	4.272	0.745	Very High Extent of Implementation
Overall	4.32		Very High Extent of Implementation

Legend: 4.20–5.00 – Very High Extent of Implementation | 3.40–4.19 – High Extent of Implementation | 2.60–3.39 – Moderate Extent of Implementation | 1.80–2.59 – Low Extent of Implementation | 1.00–1.79 – No Implementation
 Note: N=147

Table 5 reveals that the indicator, Implement the learner centered assessment policies for the Kto12 Curriculum relative to assessment and reporting has the highest mean of 4.381, and is qualitatively described Very High Extent of Implementation. This implies that implementers of LAC put assessment policies at the top of their action plan.

As stated by Cahaoay, M.B. (2020) A growing body of research has been published to discuss how education and assessment practices are changing in light of the current COVID-19 condition. For example, Bernhard & Camins, 2020 on investigating telesupervision in practicum training; Berry & Kitchen, 2020 on reconsidering education to create new transformations; Hall et al., 2020 on assisting competency-based medical education; Li et al, 2020 on utilizing blended synchronous teaching and learning.

Table 6 presents the Teacher’s Performance Rating (IPCRF) for School Year 2021-2022.

Table 6. *The Teacher’s IPCRF Performance in 4 Key Result Areas*

<i>Teacher’s Performance Indicator</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
KRA 1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy			4.22	0.591
a. Outstanding	45	31%		
b. Very Satisfactory	89	61%		
c. Satisfactory	13	9%		
KRA 2. Learning Environment			4.24	0.623
a. Outstanding	50	34%		
b. Very Satisfactory	82	56%		
c. Satisfactory	15	10%		
KRA 3. Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, & Assessment and Reporting			4.14	0.608
a. Outstanding	38	26%		
b. Very Satisfactory	93	63%		
c. Satisfactory	15	10%		
d. Unsatisfactory	1	1%		
KRA 4. Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development			4.17	0.623
a. Outstanding	43	29%		
b. Very Satisfactory	86	59%		
c. Satisfactory	18	12%		
			4.19	Very Satisfactory

As shown in table 6, 61% of the teachers had adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory level of performance in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy with weighted means of 4.22, 56% in the Learning Environment with adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory with the mean of 4.24, respectively. On KRA 3, Only 1% responded Unsatisfactory in the said Key Result Area, However, 63% had adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory with the mean of 4.14. More so, they had Very Satisfactory in KRA 4 with 59% of adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory with mean 4.17 Results further revealed that the over-all teachers performance rating is 4.19 and had an adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory level of performance in their IPCRF. This implies that the duties and responsibilities of the teachers is very satisfactory, since the performance rating of teachers is measured through this tool.

The objectives listed are essentially the obligations and responsibilities that each teacher has while they are in the classroom, claims Canoma (2017). This is a tool to assess whether one is carrying out his responsibilities with diligence, accuracy, and timeliness. Numerous studies have demonstrated that the key factor in achieving high-quality education is the performance of the teachers. When it comes to accomplishing the goals of the Philippines’ Vision 2020, teachers are extremely important. It is important to look at what influences and contributes to exasperated instructors’ performance since they are less likely to be committed, productive, and perform to the best of their skills (Haramain, 2019).

Table 7 presents significant relationship between the extent of implementation of LAC relative to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy and teacher’s IPCRF rating in KRA 1-KRA 4

Table 7. *Significant Relationship Between the Extent of Implementation of LAC Relative to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy and Teacher’s IPCRF Rating in KRA 1-KRA 4*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
1. Study and analyze the Kto12 Curriculum	0.398	0.000	Significant
2. Prepare for lessons and be more relaxed in executing lesson plans	0.212	0.010	Significant
3. Implement developmentally appropriate teaching methods that respect individual differences of the learners	0.278	0.001	Significant
4. Jointly craft learning goals in collaboration with their learners	0.303	0.000	Significant
5. Master content and performance standards and learning competencies	-0.084	0.310	Not Significant
6. Plan lessons and delivering instructions effectively	0.234	0.004	Significant
7. Assess the learning that resulted from their teaching	0.193	0.020	Significant
8. Plan weekly lessons during the LAC which can be implemented for a specified period	0.318	0.000	Significant

9. Share their experiences to improve subsequent lessons	0.293	0.000	Significant
10. Translate curriculum content into relevant learning activities	0.329	0.000	Significant

The indicator Master content, performance standards, and learning abilities is the only one with a p-value of 0.31 in Table 7, and it is not significant for the performance rating of teaching on KRA 1. This suggests that this metric has little bearing on how well teachers are performing. The 9 indicators in the table, on the other hand, demonstrate extremely high significance with p-values lower than the specified 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis, which claims there is no significant association between the level of LAC implementation in regard to content knowledge and pedagogy and the teacher's IPCRF rating in KRA 1-KRA 4, is thus rejected.

Table 8 presents Significant relationship between the performance of implementation of LAC Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion and Teacher's IPCRF in 4 Key Learning Areas.

Table 8. *Significant Relationship Between the Performance of Implementation of LAC Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion and Teacher's IPCRF Rating in KRA 1-4*

Indicators	r-value	p-value	Remarks
1. Include learner diversity and student inclusion as topic for discussion in the session	0.436	0.000	Significant
2. Emphasize that learners are the reason for all education process	0.193	0.019	Significant
3. Establish learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity	0.301	0.000	Significant
4. Underscore the importance of teacher's knowledge and understanding of learners characteristics and experiences	0.271	0.001	Significant
5. Discuss that diversity emanates from a variety of factors such as gender, community membership, religious beliefs, family configurations and special learning needs	0.396	0.000	Significant
6. Celebrate diversity in their classrooms	0.397	0.000	Significant
7. Differentiate their instruction to include all learners	0.302	0.000	Significant
8. Adjust their instruction to foster harmony in class	0.283	0.001	Significant
9. Provide remedial instruction for those who are experiencing difficulties in learning lessons	0.238	0.004	Significant
10. Prevent failure and communicating with their learners	0.304	0.000	Significant
11. Address the learners need as to strength, interests and experiences	0.367	0.000	Significant
12. Give additional information on the different indigenous groups	0.290	0.000	Significant
13. Encourage learners to be holistically developed learners	0.404	0.000	Significant

It is shown in table 8 that there is very high significance between performance of implementation of LAC Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion and Teacher's IPCRF rating in KRA 1-4. This implies that the teachers implementation of LAC is coherent to the standards and indicators in the IPCRF rating in the four key result areas.

It is presented in table 8 the significant relationship between the performance of implementation of LAC Relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization and Teacher's performance rating through IPCRF.

The study found out that there was very high significant relationship between the two variable with p-values of 0.00 in the 10 indicators. This signify that the teachers' performance and LAC implementation in the context of Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization has reasonably influenced each other.

Table 9 presents the significant relationship between the performance of implementation of LAC relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization and Teacher's IPCRF Rating In KRA 1-KRA 4

Table 9. *Significant Relationship Between the Performance of Implementation of LAC Relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization and Teacher's IPCRF Rating in KRA 1-KRA 4*

	r-value	p-value	Remarks
1. Match the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to teachers	0.361	0.000	Significant
2. Identify and responds to opportunities to link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests, and aspiration of the wider school community and other key stakeholders	0.210	0.000	Significant
3. Link new content to the local experiences that are familiar to learners to make learning more efficient and relevant	0.281	0.000	Significant
4. Modify teacher's guide and learners' materials to accommodate the unique contexts of a particular locality	0.330	0.000	Significant
5. Prepare curricula materials suited to the cultural and social context in which they teach, actively	0.310	0.000	Significant
6. Recognize that the K to 12 Curriculum is learner- centered, inclusive, and research-based	0.258	0.002	Significant
7. Realize that the K to 12 Curriculum is flexible, ICT based and global	0.404	0.000	Significant
8. Make sure that the members of the community participate in indigenization processes, so that the curriculum will be accurate and faithful to the culture in consideration	0.252	0.002	Significant
9. Inculcate that the K to 12 Curriculum is culture responsive and culture sensitive, integrative and contextualized, relevant and responsive; and	0.361	0.000	Significant
10. Work towards an implementation of a curriculum that is competence-based, seamless and decongested	0.295	0.000	Significant

It is shown that there was a consistent high significance in the ten indicators of implementing LAC and the performance rating of teachers, where all p-values are 0.00. This implies that LAC sessions among teachers influenced most the performance rating, and which LAC effectively implemented and the performance was its evidence.

Table 10 presents the significance of LAC implementation and the teachers performance rating.

Table 10. *Significant Relationship Between the Performance of Implementation of LAC Relative to Assessment and Reporting and Teacher's IPCRF Rating in KRA1-KRA 4*

	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
1. Match the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to teachers	0.318	0.000	Significant
2. Identify and responds to opportunities to link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests, and aspiration of the wider school community and other key stakeholders	0.279	0.001	Significant
3. Link new content to the local experiences that are familiar to learners to make learning more efficient and relevant.	0.340	0.000	Significant
4. Modify teacher's guide and learners' materials to accommodate the unique contexts of a particular locality.	0.313	0.000	Significant
5. Prepare curricula materials suited to the cultural and social context in which they teach, actively	0.262	0.000	Significant
6. Recognize that the K to 12 Curriculum is learner- centered, inclusive, and research-based	0.370	0.005	Significant
7. Realize that the K to 12 Curriculum is flexible, ICT based and global	0.301	0.000	Significant
8. Make sure that the members of the community participate in indigenization processes, so that the curriculum will be accurate and faithful to the culture in consideration	0.300	0.001	Significant

Table 10 demonstrated the strong significance in all indicators of implementing LAC towards the performance rating of teachers. All p-values indicates 0.00, stands greater significant relationship. The series of table from 7-10 showed a strong relationship between LAC implementation in all indicators towards the performance rating of teachers in four Key Result Areas.

Numerous studies back up the findings. According to Binauhan, R. (2019), teachers and implementers performed admirably across a range of K–12 basic education program indicators, including learner diversity and inclusion, teaching content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, curriculum contextualization, localization, and indigenization. More importantly, the research demonstrated that teachers and implementers had 21st century skills, allowing them to be recognized as 21st century teachers and implementers. Ortigas (2015) emphasizes that if the facilitator of the group (LAC) constantly performs the aforementioned responsibilities, the members will eventually learn and demonstrate these skills themselves. Individuals who are highly engaged in their jobs and are motivated by the work itself, on the other hand, tend to work harder and more productively than others and are more likely to produce the results their customers, who are the learners, want and expect, as well as the organization to which they belong.

Table 11 presents the summary of significance between the extent of implementation of LAC, the teachers' IPCRF rating

Table 11. *Summary of Significance Between LAC and Teacher's Performance*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Level of Significance</i>	<i>Annotation</i>
1. Content and Pedagogy	Significant	There are 10 sub-factors in this indicator, 1 is less significant, "Master content and performance standards and learning competencies".
2. Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion	Highly Significant	All sub-factors were found highly significant
3. Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization	Highly Significant	All sub-factors were found highly significant
4. Performance in the LAC Implementation Relative to Assessment and Reporting	Highly Significant	All sub-factors were found highly significant

In general, the teacher's LAC greatly influenced the performance of teachers in the IPCRF. The implications are supported by different researches. Binauhan, R.C (2019) found out that sharing current trends and practices on curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment revealed that there is significant difference on the assessment between teachers and implementers on the role of LAC implementation. Gumban and Pelones (2021) showed that when teachers participate in SLAC activities, their work performance increases. Implications for the professional development of teachers.

LAC conduct must have a factual foundation, according to DepEd Order No. 35 s. 2016. It must address teachers' professional needs. The themes to be discussed should be suited to the needs of the teachers and thoroughly monitored not only for compliance considerations but also to ensure that the effort is not wasted. It is critical to have an evaluation method in order to determine the value of conducting LAC in terms of both facilitator and attendee performance (teachers).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were arrived at:

By at large, the extent of LAC implementers relative to Content and Pedagogy, Relative to Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion, Relative to Curriculum Contextualization, Indigenization and Localization, and Relative to Assessment and Reporting is described Very High Extent of Implementation.

Specifically, the over-all performance of teachers in the four key result areas is Very Satisfactory.

Generally, there was a significant relationship between LAC implementation and teachers' performance, so therefore the null hypothesis that states that, there is no significant relationship between the extent of implementation of LAC, the teachers' IPCRF rating is rejected.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are given.

Teachers may be challenged to foster desirable work attitude and have a strong commitment to fulfil their duties and responsibilities to strengthened the implementation of the Learning Action Cell where they will be equipped with enough knowledge and it would yield to better education service delivery and help improve the quality of basic education.

Teachers may continue to work with dedication for a better performance is our aspirations as stewards of the children to foster lifelong learning and the children who are the hope of our land.

Teachers and school administrators may continue to plan for a meaningful LAC so that teachers continually increase its performance and sustain competent teachers in the field.

References

- Anwer,F.(2019) "Activity-Based Teaching, Student Motivation and Academic Achievement". Forman Christian College, Pakistan
- Balog,N.,(2018).Impacts of the Learning Environment on Developer's Progress.
- Baysal Z. N., et al (2016) "Classroom Teachers' Awareness of Teaching Thinking Skills Journal of Qualitative Research in Education.
- Bartz,C.J. (2016) " Bartz, C. J. (2016). Effective comprehension strategies in the social studies classroom. Culminating Projects in Teacher Development.
- Bektaş, Ö (2021) "Activity-Based Teaching with Social Studies Pre-Service Teachers for Developing the Thinking Skills of Learners".
- Binauhan, R. C (2019) " Learning Action Cell Implementation In The Public Elementary Schools In The Division Of Cavite".
- Bryan, D. (2021) "Professional Engagement". Linked in
- Canoma (2017), Assessing Elementary School Teachers' Performance Using CBPAST and IPCR: A Five Year Trajectory Report
- Clarindo, C.B et al (2020) "Learning Activity as a Means of Developing Theoretical Thinking Capacities".
- DJOUB, Z. 2021 "TEACHER DEVELOPMENT: What Teachers Need to Know
- Elkonin, D.B. (2019) "Study Activity: Its Structure and Training"
- Garet, M. S. et AL (2014.) "What makes professional development effective? Results from a national sample of teachers". American Educational Research Journal 38
- Gilavand, A (2015) "Investigating the Impact of Environmental Factors on Learning and Academic Achievement of Elementary Students".
- Ghavifekr, S. et al (2012). Management strategies for E-Learning system as the core component of systemic change: A qualitative analysis. Life Science Journal
- Gumban,H F et al (2021) School Learning Action Cell: Examining Links of a Lesson Study with Work Performance of Teachers. <https://www.workplacetesting.com/definition/328/community-linkages-workplace-safety> (2018).
- Haramain, (2019) Undesirable Factors Affecting the Performance Level of Public Secondary School Teachers in Northern Luzon, Philippines.
- Kenedy M. (2016) "How Does Professional Development Improve Teaching?". Michigan State University.
- Madriaga,K. (2021) "The Quality of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell among Elementary Schools in the Division of Quezon: Basis for Program Enhancement".
- Maulidiyah, G.,et al (2015). Effect of Problem-Based Learning of Outdoor Study on Students Outcomes in 9th Grade Senior High School. Education Journal: Theory, Research, and Development.
- Meador, D. (2018) "Ways to Enhance Personal Growth and Development for Teachers". ThoughtCo.

- Mendoza, M.G. et al (2017) “Learning action cell as professional development model”: An adaptation of lesson study. World Association of Lesson Studies.
- Oklahoma State University 2022 “Diverse Learners”.
- Ortigas, C.D. (2015). “Group Processes and Inductive Method: Theory and Practice in the Philippines. 3rd ed. Ateneo Press”
- Pariscal, D. R, et al (2022) “ Practices in the Contextualization of the English Curriculum in the Public Secondary Schools”.
- San Miguel, V.G. (2016) “Creating an Effective Learning Environment”. Education Program Specialists II-HRD Division of Malaybalay City,Bukidnon.
- Silva V. (2018) “Institutionalizing School Learning Action Cell as a Key fo Teacher’s Continuous Learning and Development”.
- Study.Com, (2018).Types of Learning Environments: from;<https://study.com/academy/lesson/types-of-learning-nvironment.html#transcriptHeader>
- Suarez, M S (2017) “The Effectiveness of Cluster Learning Action Cell (CLAC) In science on improving teaching-learning process”. The Glossary of Education Forum, 2013
- UNESCO-Internal Bureau of Education,2022 “Curriculum Planning”.
- Usman, Y.D. (2019) “Evaluation of the Effect of Learning Environment on Student’s Academic Performance in Nigeria”.
- Valazza, G. (2020) “Professional Development: Teacher Development and Confidence” MacMillan Education.
- Vega, M.G (2020) “Investigating the Learning Action Cell (lac) Experiences of Science Teachers in Secondary Schools: A Multiple Case Study”. Learner Diversity in Inclusive Classrooms: The Interplay of Language of Instruction, Gender and Disability

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Marchelle E. Baguio

Busco Central Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Aida C. Selecios

Valencia Colleges – Philippines